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Parliamentary Diplomacy and Normative Contestation after Coups d'État in West Africa

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ABSTRACT

This article examines how international parliamentary organisations (IPOs) engage with situations of constitutional rupture following coups d'état in West Africa, focusing on political transitions in Mali, Burkina Faso and Guinea (Conakry) between 2020 and 2023. It addresses how parliamentary actors, lacking coercive authority, engage in contexts marked by military takeovers, suspended constitutional frameworks and contested political legitimacy. Drawing on a constructivist and post-Westphalian perspective, the article conceptualises parliamentary diplomacy operating through discursive practices and symbolic positioning. Empirically, the analysis examines the responses of the Pan-African Parliament (PAP) and the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) based on qualitative documentary analysis of resolutions, statements and institutional reports. The findings show that, despite significant political and structural constraints, IPOs contribute to articulating expectations of legitimate governance by problematising the marginalisation of parliaments and reaffirming representative institutions as expressions of popular sovereignty.

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Introduction

Over the past decades, West Africa has experienced significant political transformations, marked by both periods of democratic institutionalisation and recurrent episodes of constitutional disruption. Between 2020 and 2023, a renewed wave of military coups in Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea (Conakry) highlighted the persistence of political instability in the subregion, undermining processes of legitimate governance and challenging the institutional arrangements consolidated in the post-Cold War period (Kassab, 2020). These developments called into question the formal legitimacy of deposed governments and exposed the limits of regional and international responses, in a context in which state sovereignty remains a central reference point, albeit increasingly subject to normative reinterpretation (Acharya, 2004).

Against this backdrop of constitutional erosion and institutional fragility, the role of international parliamentary organisations (IPOs) acquires analytical relevance. Bodies such as the Pan-African Parliament (PAP) and the Inter-Parliamentary Union (IPU) constitute transnational parliamentary forums dedicated to promoting democratic norms and affirming institutional legitimacy, operating primarily through symbolic and normative means (Cofelice, 2022). Although lacking binding authority, these organisations promote interparliamentary solidarity, political monitoring, and the

diffusion of democratic standards, and have increasingly asserted themselves as relevant actors in contemporary diplomacy, particularly in non-Western political contexts (Stavridis, 2006; Spies, 2019). Despite this, their contribution remains comparatively underexplored in the International Relations literature, which continues to privilege executive, security-focused and intergovernmental actors.

This article examines the contribution of international parliamentary actors to the reconstruction of political legitimacy in contexts of military coups in West Africa. It addresses the following research question: What role do IPOs play in responding to political and institutional crises under conditions of constitutional exception? Attention is devoted to parliamentary diplomacy as a form of institutional intervention in settings characterised by fragmented authority, suspended constitutional order and contested frameworks of political legitimacy.

The empirical analysis focuses on three principal case studies: Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea, all marked by military-led regime change and abrupt constitutional rupture. The selection of these cases reflects their relevance within the recent wave of coups in West Africa and allows for a comparative examination of different patterns of parliamentary engagement across similar institutional and regional contexts.

The relevance of this study operates on two interconnected levels. First, it contributes to debates on the limits of sovereignty and the regional production of norms in West Africa, a sub-region where colonial legacies, persistent governance challenges and external pressures intersect with efforts to assert autonomous political agency (Jackson, 2016). Second, it broadens the analytical scope of parliamentary diplomacy by foregrounding African parliamentary practices that remain underrepresented in the literature, thereby contributing to a more geographically and conceptually inclusive understanding of normative governance.

The article adopts a constructivist theoretical framework, combined with post-Westphalian approaches to sovereignty and the literature on normative promotion. This perspective enables an examination of how international organisations of a parliamentary nature intervene in the discursive construction of political legitimacy and in the reaffirmation of democratic norms under conditions of constitutional exception. It proceeds from the assumption that the normative influence of these organisations derives not from formal authority, but from their capacity to shape shared expectations, legitimise or delegitimise political actors, and signal normative reference points during moments of institutional rupture (Acharya, 2011; Holmes, 2016).

Methodologically, the study employs a qualitative and comparative approach based on the analysis of primary documentary sources, including parliamentary resolutions, statements and institutional reports produced between 2020 and 2023. This corpus allows for the identification of patterns of action, discursive strategies, and variation in the normative responses of IPOs to military coups in West Africa.

Parliamentary Diplomacy, Normative Power, and Contested Sovereignty

The analysis of the role played by IPOs in contexts of constitutional rupture in West Africa requires a theoretical framework capable of articulating three core dimensions: parliamentary diplomacy as a specific form of international action, the role of normative power in the construction of political legitimacy, and African agency in the production, adaptation and diffusion of regional norms. These dimensions make it possible to understand how such organisations intervene in situations of constitutional exception not through coercive mechanisms, but primarily by means of symbolic, discursive, and institutional instruments that operate in the sphere of political legitimation and the production of shared normative expectations.

By bringing these perspectives together, parliamentary diplomacy can be analysed as a space of normative contestation in which criteria of legitimacy, sovereignty and democratic governance are

negotiated in contexts marked by political instability, institutional fragility, and the fragmentation of state authority. In this sense, IPOs do not merely react to political crises but actively participate in shaping the discursive frameworks through which specific forms of power are legitimised or delegitimised, thereby influencing processes of political recognition at national, regional, and international levels.

This framework thus allows the analysis to move beyond strictly institutional or descriptive readings of parliamentary diplomacy, highlighting its contribution as a situated normative practice that is particularly relevant in regions where constitutional order is frequently subject to rupture and renegotiation. By focusing on West Africa, the study integrates regional specificity into broader debates on sovereignty, legitimacy, and transnational governance, highlighting the mediating role played by parliamentary organisations across distinct levels of political authority.

Parliamentary Diplomacy as a Normative Practice

Over recent decades, parliamentary diplomacy has increasingly established itself as an autonomous dimension of international and regional governance, progressively moving beyond its traditionally subsidiary role in relation to governmental or classical diplomacy (Malamud and Stavridis, 2011). This evolution reflects broader transformations in international relations, marked by the growing pluralisation of actors involved in norm production, political mediation, and the promotion of democratic values. Conceptually, parliamentary diplomacy refers to the set of practices through which parliaments and parliamentarians engage in transnational interactions, participating in processes of political dialogue, institutional cooperation and the diffusion of normative principles associated with representative democracy (Stavridis, 2006).

Organisations, such as IPU¹ or PAP², constitute institutionalised arenas of interparliamentary interaction that facilitate the circulation of ideas, the sharing of legislative best practices and the construction of symbolic consensus among elected representatives from different states (Stavridis and Jancic, 2017). These structures provide alternative channels of political communication alongside traditional governmental forums, creating opportunities for less hierarchical and potentially more inclusive forms of diplomacy. Despite the absence of binding authority, their political relevance derives from the use of instruments such as resolutions, election observation missions, public statements, and transnational parliamentary networks, which contribute to shaping internal and external perceptions of legitimacy, representation and democratic governance (Weiglas and de Boer, 2007).

The specificity of parliamentary diplomacy lies in its representative character. By bringing together directly elected politicians, these organisations claim a form of democratic legitimacy distinct from that of intergovernmental organisations, which enhances their capacity to intervene symbolically in contexts of political crisis and institutional rupture (Cofelice, 2022). In situations marked by military coups or the suspension of constitutional order, parliamentary diplomacy can function as a mechanism for reaffirming core principles of democratic governance, notably the centrality of parliaments as expressions of popular sovereignty and as privileged arenas of political deliberation.

In this context, parliamentary diplomacy tends to operate as an instrument of institutional soft power³, mobilising discursive and normative resources to contest the normalisation of constitutional

¹ Founded in 1889, IPU is the global organisation of national parliaments. Headquartered in Geneva and comprising 181 member parliaments, it promotes peace, democracy, human rights, gender equality, sustainable development, and political dialogue by articulating parliamentary action at the global level. The organisation operates under the motto “For democracy. For everyone” and pursues the mission of placing parliaments at the service of people and global peace (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2025).

² PAP is an organ of the AU established to provide a platform for parliamentary dialogue, consultation, and cooperation among African states. Composed of representatives designated by national parliaments, PAP aims to promote democratic governance, popular participation and the harmonisation of legislation across the continent, while contributing to the African Union’s objectives of integration, peace and stability (Pan-African Parliament, 2025).

³ The concept of soft power, developed by Joseph S. Nye, refers to the capacity of an actor to influence the behaviour and preferences of others through persuasion, attraction, and symbolic legitimation, as opposed to the use of force or coercion. In the context of parliamentary

exception and to promote alternative frameworks of political legitimacy (Jaskiernia, 2022). Although its material impact is often limited, such intervention contributes to sustaining international scrutiny, reinforcing narratives of democratic legality, and consolidating shared normative expectations, particularly in regions characterised by recurrent political instability and institutional fragility. Parliamentary diplomacy should therefore be understood not merely as a complementary practice to state diplomacy, but as a distinct space of normative production and political mediation in contexts of crisis.

Normative Power and the Construction of Political Legitimacy

In contexts of constitutional rupture, political contestation often shifts from direct institutional control to the definition of criteria of legitimacy. Political authority ceases to rest exclusively on formal legality or the coercive capacity of the state and becomes negotiated through normative frameworks that structure shared perceptions of legitimate governance, political responsibility, and sovereignty. In such settings, power is expressed most visibly at the discursive and symbolic level, where competing norms are asserted, contested, or reinterpreted.

The approach developed by Finnemore and Sikkink (1998) is particularly useful for understanding these dynamics, as it conceptualises norms as social constructions subject to cycles of emergence, diffusion, and internalisation. According to these authors, normative change results from the action of norm entrepreneurs⁴ who seek to redefine standards of legitimacy and influence behaviour through discursive, institutional, and symbolic mechanisms. This perspective allows political legitimacy to be analysed not as a static attribute, but as a process in constant negotiation, especially in contexts of institutional crisis.

In the African context, such normative contestation is compounded by the historical gap between the juridical–formal recognition of the state and its effective capacity for governance, a condition frequently described as “negative sovereignty⁵” (Jackson, 1991). The resulting institutional fragility has contributed to the recurrence of legitimacy crises, particularly in situations of military coups or the suspension of constitutional order. As Clapham (1996) argues, the personalisation of power and the weakness of state institutions, rooted in colonial legacies, have perpetuated patterns of personalised rule that undermine the consolidation of democratic legitimacy. Under these conditions, sovereignty no longer operates as an absolute principle, becoming progressively conditioned by regional norms, multilateral mechanisms and transnational practices that redefine the criteria of legitimate political authority (Buzan, 2004; Acharya, 2011).

It is within this evolving normative space that IPOs intervene as agents of normative promotion. Despite lacking coercive capacity, these organisations actively participate in the definition and diffusion of regional expectations of legitimate governance through public statements, resolutions, reports, and institutional positions. In doing so, they contribute to legitimising or delegitimising political actors and transitional processes, reinforcing normative frameworks associated with the rejection of unconstitutional changes of government, the restoration of constitutional order and the centrality of parliaments as expressions of popular sovereignty (Barnett and Finnemore, 2004; Cofelice, 2022).

diplomacy, this form of soft power manifests itself through the projection of values, democratic principles and institutional practices, thereby contributing to the construction of international legitimacy (Nye, 2004).

⁴ The term norm entrepreneurship refers to the process through which certain actors, whether individual or institutional, actively promote new norms within the international system, seeking to influence behaviour and to reconfigure prevailing standards of legitimacy. These “norm entrepreneurs” employ discursive, institutional, and symbolic resources to shape consensus and to establish regulatory reference points in contexts of change or contestation (Finnemore and Sikkink, 1998).

⁵ Robert H. Jackson introduced the concept of negative sovereignty to describe states that enjoy formal juridical recognition within the international system but lack the empirical capacity to govern effectively, provide public goods or exercise authority over their territory. In this formulation, sovereignty functions primarily as a legal shield rather than as an expression of effective statehood (Jackson, 1991).

In contexts of constitutional exception, such as those observed in recent years in West Africa, this normative power acquires relevance. Rather than imposing norms directly, these organisations contribute to structuring the terms of political debate, shaping perceptions of legitimacy, and influencing processes of political recognition at national, regional, and international levels.

African Agency and the Regional Production of Norms

The analysis of parliamentary diplomacy in West Africa must be situated within the broader debate on African agency and regional normative production, particularly in relation to institutional responses to political crises and constitutional ruptures.⁶ The creation of the African Union (AU)⁷ and the progressive strengthening of institutions such as PAP reflect deliberate efforts to assert endogenous mechanisms of governance⁸ and normative production, aimed at addressing recurrent challenges to political stability and institutional legitimacy on the continent (Tieku, 2012). These developments signal an attempt to move beyond externalist readings of African governance by valuing regional solutions grounded in specific historical and political experiences.

Norms such as the rejection of unconstitutional changes of government do not emerge from a simple transfer of external models, but rather from processes of adaptation, appropriation and reformulation of global principles considering African regional realities. Acharya (2004) conceptualises this dynamic as norm localisation, emphasising the active role of regional actors in reinterpreting international norms in ways that render them compatible with specific political, institutional, and historical contexts. African agency⁹ is thus expressed in the capacity to formulate regional responses to crises of legitimacy, even though such responses remain constrained by institutional limitations, external financial dependence, and political fragmentation.

Within this setting, IPOs perform a specific mediating role between national, regional, and international levels of authority. By incorporating elected representatives, they introduce a representative dimension into regional governance, complementing crisis-response mechanisms that remain intergovernmental. Their intervention contributes to associating political legitimacy with parliamentary representation, pluralism, and the restoration of constitutional order, offering alternative frameworks to the normalisation of situations of constitutional exception.

In West Africa, a region marked by recurrent episodes of political instability, this form of mediation acquires relevance. Through the production of regional discourses, parliamentary actors contribute to framing coups d'état as normative deviations and to reaffirming the centrality of representative institutions in processes of political transition. In doing so, they participate in the consolidation of regional standards of legitimacy and in the affirmation of an African agency that, while structurally constrained, plays an active role in shaping the normative terms of regional governance.

Research Design and Methodological Approach

⁶ Constitutional ruptures refer to situations in which the established constitutional order is abruptly disrupted, suspended or overturned, typically through military coups, unconstitutional changes of government or the unlawful seizure of power, resulting in a breakdown of constitutional legality and institutional continuity (Jackson, 1991).

⁷ The AU was established in 2002, succeeding the Organisation of African Unity (OAU), in the context of a broader wave of institutional reforms and the perceived need to strengthen regional mechanisms for responding to conflicts, military coups and human rights violations. As an organ of the AU, PAP held its inaugural session in 2004, giving concrete expression to the ambition of creating a supranational space for parliamentary deliberation aimed at promoting democracy, good governance and African integration (Salih, 2005).

⁸ Article 30 of the Constitutive Act of the AU stipulates that "governments which come to power through unconstitutional means shall not be allowed to participate in the activities of the Union". This provision was introduced in 2000 in response to recurrent coups d'état across Africa, consolidating the African Union's commitment to the defence of constitutional order, democracy and good governance on the continent (African Union, 2000).

⁹ Autonomous African agency refers to the capacity of African actors, both state and non-state, to define their own agendas and to develop regional solutions grounded in local values such as ubuntu. This perspective challenges Westphalian conceptions of sovereignty by emphasising human security and collective accountability and highlights the role of regional organisations in mediation and post-crisis reconstruction (Acharya, 2004).

This article adopts a qualitative and comparative research design, which is particularly suited to the analysis of normatively mediated forms of political action and the discursive construction of legitimacy in contexts of constitutional rupture. Given the symbolic and non-coercive character of parliamentary diplomacy, a qualitative approach allows for an in-depth examination of the institutional practices, narratives and normative claims advanced by parliamentary organisations during periods of political crisis (Bowen, 2009).

The empirical analysis is based on systematic document analysis of primary institutional sources produced between 2020 and 2023, corresponding to a renewed wave of military coups and constitutional disruptions in West Africa. The corpus includes resolutions, official statements, communiqués, reports, and deliberative records issued by PAP and IPU. Document analysis is employed not merely as a descriptive tool, but as a method for identifying patterns of normative positioning, discursive framing, and institutional responses to unconstitutional changes of government (Bowen, 2009). Attention is paid to how concepts such as legitimacy, constitutional order and parliamentary representation are articulated and mobilised in these documents.

The study focuses on three cases: Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea. Case selection follows a purposive logic, based on three criteria. First, all three countries experienced military coups accompanied by the suspension or marginalisation of parliamentary institutions. Second, the interventions of IPOs in these cases are sufficiently documented to permit systematic qualitative analysis. Third, the cases share regional proximity and comparable structural conditions, enabling a controlled comparison across similar political and institutional environments (George and Bennett, 2005).

The comparative dimension of the analysis does not seek to establish causal relationships between parliamentary interventions and political outcomes. Rather, it aims to assess how parliamentary actors operating at the international level articulate and promote normative expectations related to legitimacy, representation, and constitutional order under conditions of institutional disruption. In line with constructivist approaches, the focus is placed on meaning-making processes, discursive practices, and the social construction of norms, rather than on material power or enforcement capacity (Finnemore and Sikkink, 1998; Adler, 2013).

This methodological framework enables a critical assessment of parliamentary diplomacy as a form of normative intervention that operates alongside, but remains distinct from, traditional diplomatic and intergovernmental mechanisms. It also allows for an assessment of both the potential and the structural limits of parliamentary organisations operating at the international level in processes of political transition and normative contestation in West Africa.

Parliamentary Responses to Constitutional Rupture in West Africa

This section provides an empirical analysis of international parliamentary engagement in contexts of constitutional rupture in West Africa, with particular attention to the military coups that occurred between 2020 and 2023. Rather than offering a detailed description of national political developments, the aim is to examine how parliamentary diplomacy operates as a form of normative intervention in settings characterised by institutional instability, the suspension of constitutional order and the contestation of political legitimacy.

The analysis focuses on the responses of PAP and IPU, drawing on public statements, resolutions, communiqués, and other institutional documents issued in reaction to coups d'état and political transition processes. The examination of these documents makes it possible to identify how IPOs address issues of legitimate governance, sovereignty, and parliamentary representation, as well as to observe continuities and variations in the responses adopted in contexts of constitutional rupture.

A comparative approach is employed to identify patterns of action and variation in international parliamentary engagement, as well as the limits and potential of such involvement in environments marked by institutional fragility and recurrent constitutional disruption. The empirical analysis is

thus closely articulated with the theoretical framework developed earlier, allowing for an assessment of how concepts such as legitimacy, normative power and parliamentary diplomacy are translated into concrete institutional practices.

Against this background, the following subsections examine three cases from West Africa, Mali, Burkina Faso and Guinea, selected based on the recurrence of coups d'état, the suspension or marginalisation of parliamentary institutions, and the existence of documented international parliamentary interventions. Each case enables the observation of different configurations of parliamentary response and varying degrees of normative contestation in contexts of constitutional rupture.

Mali: Recurrent Coups and Parliamentary Normative Engagement

The case of Mali is analysed based on the combined action of two IPOs: PAP, in its regional role and institutional linkage to the AU, and IPU, as a global organisation dedicated to the protection of parliamentarians' rights and to strengthening the capacity of parliaments to operate in contexts of political crisis. Both organisations played a relevant role in monitoring Mali's political transition following the coups d'état of 2020 and 2021, issuing public statements, promoting inter-institutional dialogue, and calling for respect for the principle of democratic representation (ECOWAS Commission, 2021).

Following the overthrow of Ibrahim Boubacar Keïta¹⁰ in August 2020, after widespread protests against corruption, poor governance and growing insecurity, Mali entered a transitional phase dominated by military authorities (Massih et al., 2020). An initial transitional government with limited civilian participation was established, but this arrangement was disrupted by a second coup in May 2021, led by Colonel Assimi Goïta¹¹. Institutional instability deepened with the suspension of the constitution, the dissolution of parliament and the indefinite postponement of elections, prompting strong regional and international condemnation (Siegle and Cook 2024). This context of democratic regression catalysed parliamentary-level international intervention, centred on the restoration of civilian authority and the protection of parliamentary rights.

The intervention of PAP in Mali extended beyond formal declarations. In February 2021, a delegation from its Committee on International Cooperation and Conflict Resolution¹² participated in a roundtable in Addis Ababa organised by the AU, with the participation of the Economic Community of West African States and the United Nations Multidimensional Integrated Stabilisation Mission in Mali. On this occasion, PAP argued that the transitional parliament should include representatives of the political opposition, youth, and civil society, with a view to strengthening the legitimacy and representativeness of the political process (Pan-African Parliament, 2021).

In parallel, the situation in Mali was debated during the Parliament's plenary sessions in 2021 and 2022, leading to proposals for future elections to be accompanied by international parliamentary observation missions (Pan-African Parliament, 2021). These initiatives formed part of a broader effort to affirm parliamentary diplomacy as an instrument of stabilisation and of promoting

¹⁰ Ibrahim Boubacar Keïta (1945–2022) served as President of the Republic of Mali from 2013 to 2020. Democratically elected following the French military intervention against Islamist extremist groups in the north of the country, his presidency increasingly faced domestic criticism over alleged corruption, authoritarian practices, and an inability to curb worsening insecurity. He was deposed by the military in August 2020 amid widespread popular protests (Africanews, 2024).

¹¹ Assimi Goïta is an officer of the Malian Armed Forces who led the coups d'état of 2020 and 2021. Following the initial overthrow of President Keïta, he assumed the position of Vice-President within the transitional government and subsequently declared himself interim President after removing the civilian leaders of the transition. Since then, he has directed Mali's political process based on a form of military-derived legitimacy that has been contested by regional and international actors (Machado, 2020).

¹² PAP's delegation included members of the Committee on International Cooperation and Conflict Resolution, under the leadership of Djamel Bouras (Algeria). The mission aimed to assess the political and institutional situation in Mali following the second coup d'état and to propose ways of reintegrating civilian and parliamentary representatives into the transitional process. Its stated objectives included the promotion of inclusive dialogue, the restoration of constitutional order and coordination with ECOWAS and the African Union to ensure a transparent electoral timetable (Pan-African Parliament, 2021).

pluralistic representation in transitional contexts marked by power concentration and institutional fragility.

On the part of IPU, the Committee on the Human Rights of Parliamentarians treated the Malian case as emblematic of the vulnerability of parliaments in the face of politicised armed forces. The organisation issued a public statement on 7 September 2020 calling for the restoration of constitutional order and the safeguarding of parliamentary mandates. In its 2021 report, it denounced the unlawful detention of 31 members of the dissolved parliament and the systematic intimidation of opposition figures, warning of the erosion of the principle of parliamentary immunity (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2021). These concerns were reiterated in its 2022 global report, which directly urged Mali's transitional authorities to guarantee minimum conditions for the functioning of the Transitional National Council, including freedom of expression for its members (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2022).

While these initiatives did not prevent the consolidation of military power in Mali, they contributed to maintaining international scrutiny, reinforcing diplomatic pressure, and sustaining a persistent call for the restoration of constitutional legality. As noted by Pride, Smith and Foster (2017), the decline of a strictly Westphalian model of absolute sovereignty¹³ in Sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in West Africa, has opened space for parliamentary actors to emerge as producers of legitimacy in contexts of exception. In this sense, the intervention of IPOs in Mali illustrates the use of parliamentary soft power as a means of countering authoritarian tendencies, privileging approaches grounded in representation, political dialogue, and democratic legality.

Burkina Faso: Parliamentary Diplomacy under Nationalist Military Rule

The analysis of the Burkina Faso case focuses primarily on the actions of IPU, as the intervention of PAP was more limited. Following two coups d'état in 2022, led by Lieutenant-Colonel Paul-Henri Sandaogo Damiba¹⁴ in January and by Captain Ibrahim Traoré¹⁵ in September, the country entered a renewed phase of instability marked by the suspension of the Constitution, the dissolution of parliament and the consolidation of a nationalist military regime. In response, IPU issued two public statements: one in January 2022, following the first coup, calling for respect for constitutional order and the protection of parliamentary functions, and another in February 2023, in which it reaffirmed its support for political dialogue and democratic transition as the appropriate path to restoring stability (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2022; Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2023).

IPU Committee on the Human Rights of Parliamentarians also included Burkina Faso in its 2022 annual report, highlighting the importance of re-establishing a functioning legislative body, even on a transitional basis, as an indispensable step towards restoring the normal functioning of the country's political institutions.

Although the Burkinabè military authorities maintained a posture of distance from international criticism, IPU's continued emphasis on institutional rehabilitation contributed to the adoption, in May 2023, of a new decree establishing a Transitional Legislative Council with the participation of

¹³ The Westphalian model of absolute sovereignty refers to the classical understanding of sovereignty as the supreme and exclusive authority of the state within its territorial boundaries, grounded in the principles of non-intervention and formal equality among states, traditionally associated with the Peace of Westphalia of 1648. This model conceives sovereignty as indivisible and territorially bounded, a conception that has been increasingly challenged by transnational norms, regional governance mechanisms and international institutions (Buzan, 2004).

¹⁴ Paul-Henri Sandaogo Damiba is an officer of the Burkinabè armed forces who led the coup d'état of 24 January 2022, overthrowing President Roch Marc Christian Kaboré and assuming the position of head of the transitional state. He justified his actions on the grounds of deteriorating security conditions caused by jihadist attacks. In September of the same year, he was himself overthrown in a further coup led by Ibrahim Traoré (Schwikowski, 2022).

¹⁵ Ibrahim Traoré is an officer of the Burkinabè armed forces who led the second coup d'état in 2022, overthrowing Paul-Henri Sandaogo Damiba on 30 September and assuming the position of transitional president. He justified his actions by pointing to the failure to combat terrorism and pledged to reorient governance towards a more sovereign and patriotic approach. Since then, he has sought to consolidate domestic support through an explicitly nationalist and anti-Western rhetoric (Jnr, 2025).

representatives of civil society (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2023). While limited in scope, this structure represented a symbolic retreat from the purely military model imposed in September 2022.

IPU's engagement in Burkina Faso illustrates its role as a normative actor in a context where classical diplomacy and regional organisations face significant practical constraints. As in the Malian case, this intervention was non-coercive yet persistent, seeking to reintroduce principles of plural representation and constitutional legality into processes of political transition, even in settings marked by the dominance of military elites.

Guinea (Conakry): Ambiguous Legitimacy and Uneven Parliamentary Engagement

The Guinean case is distinctive due to the complex and contested relationship between legality and legitimacy that preceded and followed the military takeover. On 5 September 2021, President Alpha Condé¹⁶ was overthrown in a coup led by Colonel Mamady Doumbouya¹⁷. The new authorities dissolved parliament, suspended the Constitution, and assumed control of the state through the establishment of the National Committee of Reconciliation and Development (NCRD). Unlike other cases in the region, the military intervention occurred against a background of intense political polarisation and social unrest, exacerbated by the controversial constitutional revision of 2020 that enabled Condé to seek a third presidential term, a move widely criticised by opposition forces and civil society actors (Fouchard and Harnoy, 2021).

This context shaped the normative framing adopted by parliamentary organisations operating at the international level. IPU closely monitored developments in Guinea and recorded the suspension of the constitutional order and the closure of parliament in its 2022 annual report. The organisation documented cases of arbitrary detention, intimidation of former members of parliament and restrictions on freedom of expression, identifying these practices as indicative of a broader erosion of representative governance. In response, IPU emphasised the need to establish a transitional legislative body as a necessary condition for a credible and legitimate transition process, underscoring the centrality of parliamentary representation in restoring political accountability (Inter-Parliamentary Union, 2021).

In contrast to the Malian and Burkinabè cases, the Guinean transition was marked by a more ambiguous normative environment. While the military authorities justified their intervention as a corrective response to constitutional manipulation and democratic backsliding, they remained reluctant to articulate a clear timetable for the re-establishment of representative institutions. This ambiguity complicated the normative positioning of external actors, including parliamentary organisations, whose interventions were constrained by the absence of clear transitional benchmarks and by the regime's selective engagement with international partners.

As in Mali and Burkina Faso, IPU maintained active normative scrutiny over the Guinean situation, consistently reaffirming the role of parliaments as legitimate arenas of political representation. Although lacking direct leverage over internal political developments, its sustained engagement contributed to maintaining international attention on the institutional deadlock and to reinforcing expectations regarding the reactivation of legislative authority. This persistence reflects a broader pattern of parliamentary diplomacy operating through symbolic pressure and discursive framing rather than through direct intervention.

¹⁶ Alpha Condé was the first democratically elected president of Guinea (Conakry), serving in office from 2010 to 2021. His attempt to remain in power through a controversial constitutional revision in 2020, which enabled him to seek a third presidential term, generated strong domestic opposition and constituted one of the key factors preceding the 2021 coup d'état (Tarabey, 2021).

¹⁷ Mamady Doumbouya is a colonel of the Guinean Special Forces who led the coup d'état of 5 September 2021, overthrowing President Alpha Condé and assuming the presidency of the National Committee of Reconciliation and Development. Since then, he has led Guinea's transitional government, committing himself to a future process of institutional normalisation, albeit without a binding electoral timetable (Kum, 2021).

By contrast, PAP did not register any significant public or institutional intervention in relation to Guinea between 2021 and 2023. This relative absence may be attributed to the ambiguous legitimacy claims advanced by the Guinean military authorities and to the prioritisation of other regional crises. As a result, the Guinean case illustrates a more limited configuration of parliamentary engagement, where normative contestation was present but unevenly articulated, highlighting both the potential and the constraints of parliamentary diplomacy in contexts of constitutional rupture characterised by contested legality and delayed institutional reconstruction.

The Scope and Limits of Parliamentary Norm Entrepreneurship

The comparative analysis of the cases of Mali, Burkina Faso and Guinea reveals consistent patterns in the action of IPOs in contexts of constitutional rupture in West Africa. In all cases examined, the suspension, dissolution or marginalisation of parliaments was among the first measures adopted by military authorities, highlighting both the centrality of legislative institutions in the architecture of political legitimacy and their vulnerability to coercive power dynamics.

From an empirical perspective, the IPU displayed the most systematic and sustained engagement, particularly through its Committee on the Human Rights of Parliamentarians. The regular monitoring of violations of parliamentary freedoms, the public denunciation of arbitrary detentions and the repeated insistence on the re-establishment of legislative bodies, even on a transitional basis, illustrate a form of normative intervention grounded in symbolic and institutional instruments. This pattern constitutes a concrete expression of parliamentary soft power, oriented towards the defence of democratic representation and constitutional legality.

The PAP exhibited a more selective and uneven pattern of engagement. In the Malian case, it undertook more visible initiatives, including participation in AU forums and proposals aimed at parliamentary reintegration within the transition process. By contrast, its absence from the Guinean case and its limited involvement in Burkina Faso point to the political and institutional constraints affecting its capacity for consistent action. This variability suggests that the effectiveness of regional parliamentary diplomacy depends heavily on coordination with other continental bodies and on the existence of minimal consensus regarding the nature of the constitutional rupture.

The comparison of cases allows for three main observations. First, there is an implicit recognition among IPOs that parliaments cannot be reduced to secondary or merely formal institutions, even under conditions of constitutional exception. Second, parliamentary diplomacy does not replace state-based or intergovernmental diplomacy but can reinforce their legitimacy by mobilising shared values such as representation, pluralism and political accountability. Third, the impact of parliamentary organisations is strongly conditioned by their ability to sustain normative pressure over time and to articulate their interventions with broader multilateral networks, particularly when confronted with military regimes resistant to external oversight.

From a theoretical standpoint, the cases analysed indicate that parliamentary diplomacy can function as an instrument of normative production in contexts of institutional fragility. Its relevance lies less in its capacity to alter power balances directly than in its symbolic affirmation of minimum standards of constitutional legality and democratic representation. In this sense, international parliamentary actors function as normative mediators, contributing to the structuring of debates on political legitimacy during periods of institutional disruption.

At the same time, the limits of parliamentary diplomacy are clearly apparent. The absence of binding sanctions, limited media visibility and organisational constraints, including restricted resources and low institutional density, reduces its effective reach. In several instances, post-coup authorities disregarded parliamentary recommendations entirely, revealing a gap between symbolic influence and concrete political impact. Nonetheless, the regular presence of these organisations in

multilateral forums and their capacity to mobilise transnational parliamentary solidarities confer strategic value upon them as alternative spaces for dialogue and normative contestation.

Overall, the primary contribution of IPOs in the crisis contexts examined lies in their functions of scrutiny, denunciation and the reaffirmation of democratic principles. Through reports, public statements and parliamentary missions, these organisations place legislatures at the centre of debates on political legitimacy, emphasising that any return to constitutional order necessarily entails the reactivation of representative mechanisms. In doing so, they not only confer international visibility on domestic political crises but also provide a symbolic counterweight to authoritarian power logics. A comparative overview of the scope and intensity of parliamentary engagement across the three cases is provided in Table 1, illustrating how different degrees of institutional disruption correspond to differentiated patterns of intervention by the IPU and the PAP.

Table 1- Parliamentary Engagement in the Cases Analysed (2020–2023)¹⁸

Case	Type of constitutional rupture	IPU engagement	PAP engagement	Degree of parliamentary intervention
Mali	Two coups d'état (2020, 2021)	Public statements, reports, denunciations of detentions of MPs, calls for parliamentary reactivation.	Statements, participation in AU forums, and proposals for parliamentary reintegration	High
Burkina Faso	Two coups d'état (2022)	Public statements, reports, and calls for a transitional legislative body	Minimal engagement	Medium
Guinea (Conakry)	Coup d'état (2021)	Continuous monitoring, reports, and calls for a transitional legislative body.	No significant engagement	Low

Source: Author's compilation based on IPU and PAP documents.

Conclusion

This study examined the role of IPOs in contexts of constitutional rupture in West Africa, focusing on the cases of Mali, Burkina Faso, and Guinea between 2020 and 2023. Adopting a constructivist and post-Westphalian perspective, the analysis sought to understand how parliamentary diplomacy operates as a form of normative intervention in settings characterised by the suspension of constitutional order, the fragmentation of state authority and the contestation of political legitimacy.

The empirical analysis demonstrated that, despite the absence of coercive powers, parliamentary organisations play a relevant role in the symbolic affirmation of minimum democratic standards, particularly through the reaffirmation of the centrality of parliaments as expressions of popular sovereignty. In all three cases analysed, the dissolution or marginalisation of legislative institutions constituted a recurring feature of constitutional ruptures, simultaneously highlighting the vulnerability of parliaments in coup contexts and their importance as normative reference points in political transition processes.

¹⁸ **Methodological note:** The classification of the degree of parliamentary intervention is based on a qualitative assessment of the frequency, scope and institutional depth of the interventions undertaken by IPU and PAP in each case. This assessment considers the number of official statements and reports issued, the existence of parliamentary missions or institutional follow-up mechanisms, and the extent to which parliamentary representation and legislative reactivation were explicitly framed as normative priorities in organisational documents between 2020 and 2023.

IPU's engagement stood out for its consistency and regularity, notably through the monitoring of violations of parliamentary rights and its repeated insistence on the re-establishment of legislative bodies, even on a transitional basis. This intervention proved significant in sustaining international scrutiny and in producing shared normative expectations regarding legitimate governance. PAP, by contrast, displayed a more selective pattern of involvement, with greater visibility in the Malian case and a residual or absent presence in the other contexts examined, reflecting institutional and political constraints at the regional level.

The findings confirm that parliamentary diplomacy neither replaces state-based nor intergovernmental diplomacy nor constitutes a direct mechanism for resolving political crises. Its contribution lies instead in the production and circulation of normative frameworks that associate political legitimacy with constitutional legality, parliamentary representation, and political pluralism. In this sense, IPOs respond to political and institutional crises not by resolving them, but by shaping the normative conditions under which legitimacy is contested and reconstructed.

At the same time, the limits of this form of intervention are evident. The absence of binding instruments, the resistance of military regimes to external oversight and the organisational constraints faced by parliamentary organisations themselves reduce their material impact. In most of the cases analysed, parliamentary recommendations were ignored or only partially implemented, revealing a persistent gap between symbolic influence and concrete political transformation. These limitations do not, however, negate the relevance of parliamentary diplomacy as a space of normative contestation in contexts of constitutional exception.

From a theoretical perspective, the study contributes to debates on sovereignty, legitimacy, and transnational governance by demonstrating that state sovereignty is continuously renegotiated through discursive and normative practices. Parliamentary diplomacy emerges, in this framework, as a specific site of normative production, particularly relevant in contexts of institutional fragility where criteria of political authority remain contested.

The analysis also opens several avenues for future research. Comparative studies encompassing other regions affected by constitutional ruptures could assess the transferability of the patterns identified and evaluate the relative weight of international parliamentary involvement across different regional settings. Research focusing more closely on the interaction between parliamentary diplomacy and executive regional organisations, such as regional economic communities or peacekeeping missions, could deepen understanding of the dynamics of normative coordination. Finally, longitudinal analyses tracing the evolution of post-coup regimes would allow for an assessment of whether sustained parliamentary engagement translates, over the medium and long term, into more durable institutional effects.

The analysis undertaken demonstrates that IPOs, despite their structural limitations, play a significant role at the boundaries of political legitimacy. By insisting on the centrality of representative institutions and by framing the suspension of parliaments as a normative deficit, these organisations contribute to the preservation of a shared language of constitutional legality and democratic governance. In contexts of recurrent constitutional rupture, this symbolic contribution assumes particular importance, as it constitutes one of the few available elements of normative continuity. This finding reinforces the relevance of parliamentary diplomacy as an object of analysis in the study of contemporary political transitions and emerging forms of transnational governance.

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